

Skaian Gates
ENGLISH

Language Editing Certificate

This document certifies that the manuscript entitled

“Artificial Intelligence for Rapid Detection of Earthquake Wave Basic Phases: Ayvacık Seismic Network Example”

by

Utku ÜNAL & Tolga BEKLER

has been personally proofread and edited by a native speaker of English born in Dublin, Ireland with experience of language editing scientific manuscripts since 2010 to ensure the language is of an acceptable standard.

Date: 21 May 2024

Certificate no: 24-05-131007

Catherine Yiğit
BA Natural Science (mod Geol)
Trinity College Dublin
University of Dublin
Ireland

Skaian Gates
ENGLISH

cyigit@skaiangates.com

<http://english.skaiangates.com>